

WinWin 4 WorkLife

D3.2 Implementation plan for data collection

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R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Dissemination Level		
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CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
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This deliverable D3.2 was originally planned to be submitted by M4. By then, most information about survey target groups, sampling procedures, the communication strategy to engage employers and employees in Finland, Germany, Luxembourg, Portugal and Slovakia was already collected. However, it did not yet include a precise timeline/survey protocol defining main tasks, subtasks if needed and responsibilities for these (sub)tasks. This required additional discussions with the local data collection teams. Moreover, during the design of the questionnaires, additional elements became apparent that affected the implementation plan. The submission of deliverable D3.2 was therefore delayed to M6 which allowed further alignment of this deliverable with the design of the questionnaires

Executive summary

The WinWin4WorkLife (WW4WL) will gather data on Remote Work Arrangements (RWAs) through comprehensive employer and employee studies, including surveys, time diaries, and interviews, across five countries to understand socio-economic impacts and cultural differences. The employer study will focus on six key topics: organisational support, productivity, remote work potential, skills shortage, willingness to pay, and company location decisions, using adaptable questionnaires and robust validation methods. The recruitment strategy involves sending survey invitations by email and/or postal letters to employers in five geographical areas, with follow-ups to non-responders to ensure high response rates. The surveys will be conducted over three months, leveraging various outreach channels and tailored recruitment methods for each country to gather comprehensive data on RWAs.

The employee study aims to explore the socio-economic impacts of RWAs on employees, examining their views, time use, and household dynamics across different demographics and countries. The research will utilise online surveys, time diaries, and in-depth interviews, focusing on aspects such as quality of life, productivity, role of digital skills, relocation decisions, and socio-economic implications, aiming to reveal cultural and regional differences and guide future remote work policies. Additionally, the digital nomad survey in Portugal aims to investigate the impact of digital nomads on urban structures, gentrification, and economic changes, particularly in Lisbon Metropolitan Area. This involves collecting socioeconomic data, travel behaviour, and satisfaction levels through interviews and surveys, to inform policies on managing the benefits and drawbacks of digital nomadism.

Section 1 provides a background information that is fundamental to the entire WW4WL and is the guiding principle of the data collection campaigns, a description of the five case studies for which data will be collected, and a listing of the different data collection methods. Sections 2 and 0 then describe the protocols for the employer and the employee study, respectively. Protocol for the digital nomad survey is introduced in Section 4. Attention is also paid to ethics, privacy, and GDPR that are summarized in Section 5 and the details of which are covered in D1.2 *Data Management Plan* and D1.3 *Ethics and security management report* which provide more guidelines in terms of data management and protection, respectively.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviations	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
DCC	Data Collection Campaign
DE	Germany
DPO	Data Protection Officer
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
EC	European Commission
FI	Finland
HR	Human Resources
ICT	Information & Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
LU	Luxemburg
LUTI	Land Use Transport Interaction
MOTUS	Modular Online Time Use Survey
MUP	Mannheim Enterprise Panel
NACE	Nomenclature statistique Activités économiques dans la Communauté Européenne
OACL	Online Activity Classification List
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PT	Portugal
RWA	Remote Work Arrangement
SK	Slovakia
SP	Stated Preference
SRS	Simple Random Sample
TBC	To Be Confirmed
US	United States
WP	Work Package
WW4WL	WinWin4WorkLife

1. Background information

The overarching narrative of the project is to study the impacts of RWAs from the perspectives of both employers and employees. In addition to a limited set of secondary data, WinWinWW4WL will collect research data from employers and employees which will then be analysed, interpreted, and used to address research hypotheses defined in three empirical work packages:

- The employer’s perspective (WP4): Understanding interactions between RWAs and working conditions, defined in Section 2 *Protocol for the employer study*,
- The employee’s perspective (WP5): Understanding interactions between RWAs and living conditions, defined in Section 0 *Protocol for the employee study* and Section 4 *Protocol for the digital nomad study*,
- Forecasting spatial and environmental impacts of RWAs (WP6), a cross-cutting research work package based on transport and land-use modelling.

Research hypotheses defined within these three WPs are summarised in **Table 2** and **Table 20** for the employer and employee studies respectively, and Section 4.1 for the digital nomad study.

1.1. Case studies

Table 1 below summarises the key characteristics and specific research focus for each of the five case study countries: Finland, Germany, Luxembourg, Portugal, and Slovakia. In addition to the general research hypotheses about economic, social, and spatial impact of remote work (to be studied in WP4, WP5, and WP6, respectively), each case study has some very specific research hypotheses. These case study specific research hypotheses are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Summary of case studies

Case study Finland (FI) – Multi-locality	
Campaign manager	Riku Reunamäki (UH)
Social media manager	Riku Reunamäki (UH) / Olle Järv (UH)
Data manager(s)	Olle Järv (UH) / Tuomas Väisänen (UH)
Case-study specific research hypothesis	<p>Second homes reversal, multi-local living and working remotely from a second home which has already been observed during the pandemic</p> <p>RH-FI.1: Many employees have embraced multi-locality by remaining in their secondary home for extended periods of time or ‘switched’ their main home location, using their home in the capital only occasionally.</p> <p>RH-FI.2: Due to increased possibilities for remote work, employees have purchased second homes in rural areas (places they actually like/prefer to live).</p>

	RH-FI.3: Increased remote work possibilities have resulted in the change of purpose of rural second homes from purely leisure to mixed leisure and work.
Spatial coverage (model for WP6)	South Savo region in FI (popular rural second home location for remote employees) and the Helsinki Metropolitan Area (Helsinki, Vantaa, Kauniainen, Espoo)
Specific target groups	Workers with several remote working places (urban and rural, which include mostly second homes but also coworking spaces or public spaces)
Case study Germany (DE) - Tight and expensive housing market in urban areas	
Campaign manager	Employer study: Daniel Erdsiek (ZEW) Employee study: Ana Tsui Moreno (TUM)
Social media manager	Master student (TUM) to be enrolled in the project
Data manager(s)	Employer study: Leili Erfanian (ZEW) Employee study: Ana Tsui Moreno (TUM)
Case- study specific research hypothesis	The main research hypothesis derives from the tight and expensive housing market in the Munich Metropolitan Area. Munich is the most expensive city in Germany to rent new-build home, with a median of 23.4 eur/sqm in 2024, compared to the second most expensive city, Berlin, with a median rent of 21 eur/sqm, or the median rent of 13.2 eur/sqm across all cities (BNP Paribas, 2024). One specific research hypothesis is formulated: RH-DE.1: RWAs can help escape the expensive housing market in the city of Munich.
Spatial coverage (model for WP6)	Munich Metropolitan Area, including Augsburg, Ingolstadt, Landshut and Rosenheim and surrounding areas.
Specific target groups	Workers for whom RWAs enables them to “escape” expensive housing market
Case study Luxembourg (LU) - Satellite office, cross-border mobility	
Campaign manager	Laetitia Hauret (LISER)
Social media manager	Nicolas Stamets (LISER)
Data manager(s)	Marc Schneider (LISER) for data sharing, storage, and archiving Anasse El Maslohi (LISER) for data cleaning and harmonization
Case-study specific research hypothesis	Around 200,000 cross-border workers travel to work in Luxembourg on a regular basis, which is almost half of the country’s workforce. Moreover, commuting by car is particularly strong among cross-border workers due to their longer commuting distances. Three research hypotheses are formulated: RH-LU.1: Any positive impact of RWAs on cross-border commuting is partly mitigated because of differences in taxation in social security for cross-border commuters compared to residents of Luxembourg. RH-LU.2: RWAs can help escape the expensive housing market in LU by relocating to cheaper places across the border. RH-LU.3: Satellite office is a successful new remote working strategy in cross-border areas such as LU.
Spatial coverage (model for WP6)	Greater Region of Luxembourg
Specific target groups	Satellite office users Cross-border workers
Case study Portugal (PT) – Digital nomads	
Campaign manager	João de Abreu e Silva (IST ID)

Social media manager:	PhD student to be nominated, possible master student to be enrolled in the project.
Data manager(s)	João de Abreu e Silva (IST-ID)
Case-study specific research hypothesis	<p>Portugal (and Lisbon as the capital) has benefited from accommodating laws and low tax rates for international remote workers (digital nomads). Lisbon alone numbers about 16,000 such workers. Although this has revitalised the city, it has also impacted property prices.</p> <p>RH-PT.1: RWAs can impact travel and (second home) location decisions (e.g., Lisbon's beachfront), Lisbon is currently very attractive to digital nomads.</p> <p>RH-PT.2: Digital nomads are contributing to gentrification in Lisbon traditional neighbourhoods.</p> <p>RH-PT.3: Use of former second homes (similar to South Savo) or lower priced homes outside Lisbon (similar to Munich).</p>
Spatial coverage (model for WP6)	Lisbon Metropolitan Area
Specific target groups	Digital nomads and local workers engaging in RWAs
Case study Slovakia (SK) – Brain drain	
Campaign manager	Employer study: Michal Hrnčiar (TREX) Employee study: Eva Malichova (UNIZA)
Social media manager	Eva Malichova (UNIZA)
Data manager(s)	Employer study: Michal Hrnčiar (TREX) Employee study: Christina Georgouli (UNIZA)
Case-study specific research hypothesis	<p>Slovakia is a small country with good connectivity, particularly on the Bratislava, Zilina, and Kosice line. Bratislava has experienced a boom in employment attractiveness in recent years, offering higher salaries compared to the rest of the country and drawing many younger workers to move to the capital, with a similar but smaller pattern also occurring in Zilina and Kosice. It is usual for such workers to return to their hometown on weekends. RWAs could therefore in theory reduce weekly commuting and revive smaller towns if studied on a national scale.</p> <p>RH-SK.1: RWAs can mitigate brain drain from rural areas to cities of Bratislava, Zilina, and Kosice.</p> <p>RH-SK.2: RWAs may, under certain conditions, contribute to mobility-related GHG emission reductions</p>
Spatial coverage (model for WP6)	Cities Bratislava, Zilina, and Kosice and rural areas in Slovakia
Specific target groups	Young and middle-age highly educated workers with a RWA and commuting between urban and distant rural areas

1.2. Data collection methods

The data that WW4WL will collect regarding RWAs by employers and employees is not based on one single survey, but a combination of different data collection methods. The project starts with an employer study consisting of an online survey, and then continues with an employee study consisting of an online survey, time diary, and interviews (for more details about the timing please refer to **Table 19** and **Table 43**).

Employer study (see Section 2.2):

Employer survey: an online questionnaire, including vignette and stated preference experiment.

Employee study (see Section 3.2):

- 1. Employee survey:** an online questionnaire, including stated preference experiments,
- 2. Time diary:** a time diary completed for at least one day when employees work at the office and another day when they work remotely (e.g., at home),
- 3. In-depth interviews** with employees who often work remotely.

As per the Grant Agreement (GA), this will eventually result in four open datasets (#7 Employer Survey, #8 Employee Survey, #9 Employee Time Use Diary, and #10 Employee In-depth Interview). For more details, please refer to deliverable *D1.2 Data Management plan*.

In addition, there will also be an online **survey for digital nomads**. While the previous four types of data collection are conducted in all case studies of the project, the digital nomads survey will only take place in Portugal.

2. Protocol for the employer study

2.1. Aim

The main objective of WP4 on the 'employer perspective' is to enhance the understanding of the socio-economic impacts of RWAs by focusing on the work sphere. There is today a lot of ambiguity about RWAs from an employer's perspective, and therefore a need to gain more insights into how employers think about RWAs.

The employer study is based on an online survey collecting data on the employers' views and practices regarding RWAs, considering differences between companies of different sectors, sizes, and locations. Because the survey will be conducted in five different geographical areas with different labour markets and welfare systems, the study also aims to reveal the role of cultural differences.

2.1.1. Research hypotheses

The WW4WL project has limited the employer research scope to six key topic areas that will be further explored in six separate tasks within WP4. Each of these six topic areas refer to a specific research hypothesis, partly based on insights obtained during the literature review in WP2, partly based on previous research by consortium partners on these topics. The way the hypotheses are formulated makes clear which variables are important for the WP4 analysis, which in turn serves to guide the types of questions asked in the survey (**Table 2**). For each of these six topics, we also hypothesize that results will differ across company sizes, sectors, culture (five survey countries), and location (urban/rural). Location information is particularly relevant for feeding in the WP6 land use and transport models. In other words: heterogeneity linked to the company environment runs as a transversal theme through the six topic areas.

Table 2 provides an overview of the research hypotheses and which analytical methods will be used for which task and topic area.

Table 2: Research hypotheses and research questions from the employer perspective

Task	Topic area	Research hypothesis (RH)	Main research question(s)	Main analytical methods
T4.1	Organisational support to RWAs	RH 4.1: Differences in working conditions (in terms of health and safety of workers, wages, working time, job security, skills development and training, employment benefits, 'telework package') and organisational practices (in terms of number of hierarchy levels and monitoring policy) provide a basis for a typology of	How do companies vary in their offer of remote work to their employees and their organisational support to remote work? What determines a company's friendliness to remote work?	Factor analysis (e.g., PCA) and cluster analysis

		companies' friendliness to RWAs.		
T4.2	Workforce productivity and well-being	RH4.2: Differences in employers' concerns about productivity and well-being (in terms of reducing sickness absence, burn out, and impacts on team performances) explain differences in companies' friendliness to RWAs.	To which extent is a company's friendliness to remote work related to the company's concerns about productivity and well-being of its workforce?	Standard econometric methods
T4.3	RWA potential difference	RH4.3: Type of company location (urban/non-urban) and other company characteristics (e.g., size, sector) affect the willingness of companies to offer remote work.	What are the differences and similarities in the feasibility of remote work across companies? What are barriers and opportunities for the implementation of RWAs at company-level?	Standard econometric methods
T4.4	Skills shortage	RH4.4: Companies may consider RWA as a tool to attract employees and fill job vacancies, especially if they see challenges concerning skills shortages.	Is remote work considered by companies as a solution to deal with skills shortage to tap in a larger pool of talent?	Linear regression, Discrete choice models
T4.5	Willingness to pay for remote work	RH4.5: Companies' wage offers differ by the employees' demand for remote work , but also by occupation type, gender, and overall RWA use in that occupation.	To what extent does employees' demand for remote work influence the wage offer made by the employer? Does it introduce inequalities between gender, occupations and locations? How does the spread of RWAs affect these inequalities?	Linear regression, Discrete choice models
T4.6	Company location decisions	RH4.6: RWAs might impact locational strategies of companies , but this will depend on characteristics of the office alternatives (e.g., size, costs), locational characteristics (e.g., accessibility levels, distance from the Central Business District, proximity to customers).	What are companies' locational strategies in response to different scenarios of remote work adoption in their company? Under which scenario of remote work, will companies decide to downsize their floorspace or relocate to an alternative location?	Linear regression, Discrete choice models
T6.1 (with input from T4.1 and T4.5)	RWA uptake (employer perspective)	RH6.1: The future uptake of RWAs will differ by country, sector, location (urban/rural), and gender. This might also have implications for wage distribution across different segments of the labour market.	What are future trends in the diffusion of RWAs by different segments of the economy (in terms of sector, occupation, gender, location)? What are implications for the wage distribution and wage inequality?	Descriptive Statistics, Forecasting Model

T6.3 (with input from T4.6)	Rural vs urban land use impacts	RH6.4: RWA impacts organisation and use of land in urban and rural areas.	What is the impact of employer's business location choices on land use patterns of cities and rural areas?	Spatial modelling (LUTI - model)
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The resultant analyses in WP4 will lead to a summary of the main socio-economic effects of RWAs from an employer's perspective (T4.7). It will detail a baseline that shows the business-as-usual projection. But it will also focus on how typologies of companies regarding remote work can evolve over time, the potential effects of remote work on company productivity and mental health, and the spatial impacts of remote work in terms of company re-locations.

2.2. Study design

The employer study is based on an employer survey. The employer survey will be conducted online (web and mobile) and will be run using the MOTUS platform, a data collection platform managed by hbits and to which WW4WL has free access. We will generate a survey instrument that is adaptable to different national contexts of the five survey countries (i.e., Finland, Germany, Luxembourg, Portugal, Slovakia).

Most survey questions are applicable to all companies. However, at the end of the questionnaire, there is a vignette about the employer's salary offers to candidates with different profiles and remote work preferences and a Stated Preference (SP) experiment about relocation decisions of companies under different scenarios of remote work. However, relocation decisions of especially large companies with multiple establishments depend on other factors than remote work and those SP experiments do not need to be shown to large companies but only to small and medium-sized companies with a single establishment. Therefore, a screening question about company size and/or number of establishments at the start of the survey will trigger survey branches so that large companies are automatically excluded from the SP experiment and directed to the vignette. Moreover, the SP experiments will only be shown to companies located in the specific case study area within the country of research (i.e., Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo region in Finland; Munich Metropolitan Area in Germany; Luxembourg; Lisbon Metropolitan Area in Portugal; cities of Bratislava, Zilina, and Kosice in Slovakia) and not to all companies in that country. This restriction applies to obtain the necessary inputs for the spatial models in WP6, which will be developed for these specific case study areas and not for the whole country.

The questionnaire will be available in the following **languages:** English, Finnish, French, German, Portuguese, and Slovak. ZEW will coordinate the design of the questionnaire in English. Local data collection teams will be responsible for translation in their own languages: UH for Finnish, LISER for French, ZEW for German, IST-ID for Portuguese, and TREX for Slovak.

Survey questions will be developed in consultation with partners from across work packages. The survey design will be followed by four cycles of validation and tests. First, an **expert review** will take place within the wider WW4WL team and drawing from the advisory board expertise. The review's main objective is to validate the content of the questions and the format of the survey against the project objectives and research hypotheses. Second, the survey will be ported to the MOTUS platform into a **proof-of-concept** to test the survey implementation and demonstrate the overall flow (see Section 0). Third, the resulting draft instrument in the MOTUS platform will be subjected to **formal pilot testing**. A first pilot test will consist of a small sample of companies (three to five per case study location) covering different native language speakers, company sizes, and sectors selected to carry out the employer survey following a think-aloud protocol in the presence of interviewers from the different consortium partners. These interviews might take place in-person or online. These interviews will serve as a cognitive test, confirming the usability of the survey and ensuring that key terms are understood correctly in every language. This first pilot test will be coordinated by ZEW, with support from data collection teams. Fourth, a **second pilot test** with a larger sample of companies (10 to 15 companies per case study location) will be run to verify whether the outcomes of the SP experiments can be used for the desired type of analysis expected. This is needed given that to our knowledge it will be the first time a SP experiment is conducted on the role of remote work in location decisions of employers. A larger pilot test is in this case needed. This second pilot test will be coordinated by IST-ID and will take place in all case study locations given that the formulation of the alternatives in the choice experiment might be case-dependent.

2.2.1. Study population

The study population consists of **private and public companies with 5 or more employees** covering all NACE¹ sectors, and oversampling for sectors with high teleworkability index (as indicated in Figure 1, these are sectors 1-3 in the list below), and one sector with low teleworkability as a comparative baseline (sector 4 in the list below). All other sectors are grouped together (sector 5 in the list below).

NACE industry sectors to include in all five case study locations are:

1. K-Financial and insurance activities,
2. J-Information and Communication,
3. M-Professional, scientific, technical, and service activities,
4. C-Manufacturing,
5. All others.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3859598/5902521/KS-RA-07-015-EN.PDF>

Figure 1: Teleworkability by NACE sectors for Germany (Alipour et al., 2023)

2.2.2. Sampling frame

Sampling criteria / Stratification parameters: The sample of employers is stratified according to 1) NACE sectors and 2) company size (in this order). There will be no sampling of micro-companies with less than 5 employees. Company size categories to use for all five case studies are: small (5-49 employees), medium-sized (50-249 employees), and large (250+ employees) companies. For the employer survey, the geographical scale is national by default, but if needed a case study can oversample according to its needs, for example, a focus on Lisbon Metropolitan Area for Portugal, Munich Metropolitan Area in Germany, or Helsinki Metropolitan Area, and South Savo region in Finland.

The **sampling sources** differ by case study location; **target sample sizes** per survey country have been determined based on previous comparable company surveys (see Table 3): 1,000 companies in Finland, 1,500 in Germany, 250 in Luxembourg, 1,000 in Portugal, and 500 in Slovakia.

Table 3: Overview of the sampling sources for the employer survey

Survey country	Sampling source	Consent to be contacted	Public and private sector?	Target Sample size	Sampling criteria available?		Location data available? (e.g., urban vs rural, Sector by NACE code)
					Sector by NACE	Size	
Finland	External survey company	No	Yes	1,000	Yes	Yes	Yes
Germany	The Mannheim Enterprise Panel (MUP) is a panel dataset maintained by ZEW since 1992 that covers almost the entire population of enterprises in Germany. The MUP is the most extensive firm-level panel dataset for Germany outside of official statistics.	No	Only private	1,500 + Munich add-on (200)	Yes	Yes	Yes
Luxembourg	Labour Microdata Platform on Labour and Social Protection of the Inspection Générale de la Sécurité Sociale. It contains administrative micro-data with record information on employees working in Luxembourg and on the characteristics of the companies in which they work.		Yes	250	Yes	Yes	No
Portugal	Panels from external survey company based on public (purchasable) databases.	TBC	TBC	1,000	TBC	TBC	TBC
Slovakia	TREXIMA internal database of National project “National Occupation System” ² TREXIMA internal database of Job portal “WORKI” where thousands of employers are registered ³	Yes, for marketing purposes	Yes	500	Yes	Yes	Yes

² <https://www.sustavapovolani.sk/sektorove-rady/>

Trexima Bratislava implemented the national project National Occupation System from 2012 to 2022. Within the framework of the project, sectoral councils were created as associations composed of representatives of the most important companies in individual sectors of the national economy. These are the hundreds of employers who were involved in the project and in most cases they were representatives of HR departments. For the purposes of the WW4WL project, a database of these contacts will therefore be used.

³ www.worki.sk. TREXIMA Bratislava, has been developing and implementing effective methods in the fields of labour market forecasting, wage research and statistics, employment, and comprehensive productivity since 1992. The beginnings of our Job portal date back to 2003, when TREXIMA started building a new information system called the Integrated System of Job Positions (ISTP) for the needs of

In terms of **power analysis**, our aim is to obtain a sample of sufficient size to permit us to make estimates with reasonable precision within subgroups. These subgroups are company size (3) and sector (5). The purpose of this analysis is to expand the knowledge in this field and provide evidence on the social, economic, and spatial impacts of remote work (in terms of well-being, productivity, and relocation respectively) and the likely group differences between company size and sector. We therefore take the approach that a standardised effect size of 0.20 is a minimum effect of substantive interest at population-level but we are likely to find a higher effect size of 0.30 because of the oversampling in the most teleworkable sectors. Assuming a simple random sample (SRS), a cell size of 188 respondents would yield 90 percent power to detect such an effect assuming a type I error of 5%⁴. This implies an achieved sample size of $3 \times 5 \times 188 = 2,820$ for all five survey countries together. The sum of the previously mentioned target sample sizes per case study is thus more than sufficient.

We will attempt to maximise response rates given the constraint that we cannot offer a monetary incentive. Previous smaller scale studies have achieved response rates ranging between +/- 10% and over 40% (Hudec et al., 2019; Trexima, 2020; ZEW, 2024). If we assume a 10 percent response rate, we will need to issue around 28,200 survey invitations. Initial analysis of our sampling sources listed in **Table 3** indicates that this is a realistic proposition (see the next two sections for more details on sampling methods and recruitment).

Where the real subpopulation (sector x size) is no larger than the required number from which a 10 percent response rate would provide sufficient power to detect group difference, a census approach will be taken. Where subpopulations (sector x size) are larger than this, a sampling fraction will be calculated based on the number required as a proportion of the number of possible participants. A census approach will not be taken in these cases in adherence with the data minimization principle of the GDPR and to avoid contributing to wider survey fatigue through oversampling. Contact details will be randomised and every nth contact will be selected, while also checking the balance of location types (urban/rural).

In terms of **weighting**, for full population estimates, the assumption of an SRS is not realistic, and we will need to apply weights to correct for the necessary oversampling

employment offices. As a state labour portal with the modified name Internet Guide to the Labor Market, we have been here for our customers since 2013. After 20 years of ISTP development, TREXIMA Bratislava transformed this website to WORKI.

⁴ Using the calculator at <https://clincalc.com/stats/samplesize.aspx> with 1) One study group vs. population 2) Primary endpoint: dichotomous (more productive/less productive – more wellbeing/less wellbeing – relocation: yes/no) 3) Anticipated incidence: known population 20%, study group 30% (we might expect that our study will find higher % compared to what is reported in the literature because of the oversampling in the most teleworkable sectors) 4) Type I/II error rate: alpha 0.05; power 90%. Sample size = 188

of some sectors and company size classes. In the post data collection phase, we will therefore calculate weights using the Iterative Proportional Fitting weighting procedure available in R (package 'ipfr') and Stata (package 'ipfraking') developed by Kolenikov (2014).

Finland

Table 4: Stratification of companies in Finland by NACE sector

Sector by NACE code	Total (Finland)	Share %	Target employer survey
C-Manufacturing	6,978	12.7	250
J-Information and Communication	2,849	5.2	200
K- Financial and insurance activities	1,081	2.0	100
M-Professional, scientific, technical service activities	4,496	8.2	250
Other NACE-codes	39,426	71.9	200
Target sample size	54,830	100	1,000

Sources used to collect statistical data: https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_alyr/ and https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_alyr/statfin_alyr_pxt_13www.px

Table 5: Stratification of companies in Finland by size

Company size	Total (Finland)	Share %	Target employer survey
5-49 employees	50,479	92.1	600
50-199 employees	3,742	6.8	300
200 employees or more	609	1.1	100
Target sample size	54,830	100	1,000

Sources used to collect statistical data:

https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_alyr/statfin_alyr_pxt_13wx.px

Business information system: <https://www.ytj.fi/en/index/opendata.html>, <https://tietopalvelu.ytj.fi/>, <https://www.finder.fi/>, or <https://www.fonecta.fi/> (for employee numbers)

Germany

Table 6: Stratification of companies in Germany by NACE sector

Business sectors	Total (Germany)	Share %	Target employer survey
C-Manufacturing	97,024	11.9	300
J-Information and Communication	25,910	3.2	300
K- Financial and insurance activities	8,370	1.0	300
M-Professional, scientific, technical service activities	74,439	9.2	300
Other NACE-codes	607,285	74.7	300
Target sample size	813,028	100	1,500

Sources used to collect statistical data: Business register from the Federal Statistical Office of Germany.

Table 7: Stratification of companies in Germany by size

Company size	Total (Germany)	Share %	Target employer survey
5-49 employees	723,290	89.0	550
50-249 employees	73,034	9.0	550
250 employees or more	16,704	2.1	400
Target sample size	813,028	100	1,500

Sources used to collect statistical data: Business register from the Federal Statistical Office of Germany.

Luxembourg

Table 8: Stratification of companies in Luxembourg by NACE sector

Sector by NACE code	Total (Luxembourg)	Share %	Target employer survey
C-Manufacturing	413	4.9	45
J-Information and Communication	483	5.7	45
K- Financial and insurance activities	377	4.5	45
M-Professional, scientific, technical service activities	1,107	13.2	45
Other NACE-codes	6,029	71.7	70
Target sample size	8,409	100	250

Sources used to collect statistical data: Répertoire des entreprises luxembourgeoises, STATEC, 2020.

Table 9: Stratification of companies in Luxembourg by size

Company size	Total (Luxembourg)	Share %	Target employer survey
5-49 employees	7,376	87.7	84
50-249 employees	843	10.0	83
250 employees or more	190	2.3	83
Target sample size	8,409	100	250

Sources used to collect statistical data: Répertoire des entreprises luxembourgeoises, STATEC, 2020.

Portugal

Table 10: Stratification of companies in Portugal by NACE sector

Sector by NACE code	Total (Portugal)	Share %	Target employer survey
C-Manufacturing	31,239	4.7	200
J-Information and Communication	12,794	1.9	200
K- Financial and insurance activities	2,079	0.3	200
M-Professional, scientific, technical service activities	39,851	6.0	200
Other NACE-codes	659,428	88	200
Target sample size	745,391	100	1,000

Sources used to collect statistical data: <https://www.ine.pt/>; <https://www.pordata.pt/>; <https://www.bportugal.pt/>

Table 11: Stratification of companies in Portugal by size

Company size	Total (Portugal)	Share %	Target employer survey
5-49 employees	737,097	98.9	600
50-249 employees	7,176	1.0	300
250 employees or more	1,118	0.1	100
Target sample size	745,391	100	1,000

Sources used to collect statistical data: <https://www.ine.pt/>; <https://www.pordata.pt/>; <https://www.bportugal.pt/> - n.b.: The Portuguese statistics do not distinguish companies with less than 5 employees (the lowest class is 1-10 people). This is an estimate, assuming that half of the companies with less than 10 employees have 5 or less employees. Since there is no easily available information by sector about the size of the companies, the reduction was distributed proportionally to the weight of each sector.

Slovakia

Table 12: Stratification of companies in Slovakia by NACE sector

Sector by NACE code	Total (Slovakia)	Share %	Target employer survey
C-Manufacturing	5,925	14,8	100
J-Information and Communication	1 151	2,9	90
K- Financial and insurance activities	210	0,5	90
M-Professional, scientific, technical service activities	2,927	7,3	70
Other NACE-codes	29,878	74,5	150
Target sample size	40,091	100	500

Sources used to collect statistical data: STATISTICAL OFFICE OF THE SLOVAK REPUBLIC, 2023 https://datacube.statistics.sk/#!/view/sk/VBD_SLOVSTAT/og2021qs/v_og2021qs_00_00_00_sk

Table 13: Stratification of companies in Slovakia by size

Company size	Total (Slovakia)	Share %	Target employer survey
5-49 employees	34,867	87.0	250
50-249 employees	4,372	10.9	200
250 employees or more	852	2.1	50
Target sample size	40,091	100	500

Sources used to collect statistical data: STATISTICAL OFFICE OF THE SLOVAK REPUBLIC, 2023 https://datacube.statistics.sk/#!/view/sk/VBD_INTERN/pr0902qs/v_pr0902qs_00_00_00_sk

2.2.3. Recruitment strategy

Survey invitations will be sent by email and/or postal letter (**Table 14**).

Table 14: Recruitment method by survey country

Survey country	Sampling method	Target sample size	Budget foreseen in GA
Finland	To be discussed with survey company	1,000	EUR 40,000
Germany	Invitation and reminders via postal letter and emails	1,500 + 200 (Munich add-on)	EUR 60,000
Luxembourg	Invitation and reminders via postal letter, available in three languages (DE, FR, EN)	250	EUR 20,000
Portugal	To be discussed with survey company	1,000	EUR 40,000
Slovakia	Invitation and reminders by official email first, phone calls and postal letters as a back-up in case of low response rate.	500	From PMs

In those survey countries where we have no information about the consent from the data subjects in the sampling source to be contacted for (survey) research:

- Partners with access to this sampling source (e.g., TREX, ZEW) need to give clearance to the WW4WL project that they remain responsible for this sampling source.
- One email/letter will be sent prior to data collection, informing sample members of our intention to invite them to participate, with an explanation of the project and its aims, along with information regarding how the participant has been selected and instructions on how to opt out if they choose to do so. For those who have not opted out at this stage, an invitation email/letter will be sent a few days later.

The data collection will last for three months. The sample will be issued in stages. Non-responders will be followed up with a minimum of 1 reminder after 15 days of the invitation (in case of postal invitation letters) and a minimum of 2 reminders (in case of email invitation).

To follow-up non-response and send reminders to the appropriate non-responders, the initial invitation (be it a postal letter or e-mail) must include a username and password that the participant can use to log into the employer survey. Therefore, when drawing the sample for each survey country, each sampled company must be given a unique ID together with a username and password. By reading the unique IDs into MOTUS (to be done by the local data collection teams), non-response can be monitored in the MOTUS platform. It is important to state that the login name and password for each employer can be exported, making it possible to reach employers separately by e-mail outside MOTUS. This is needed in some cases where employers

expect an email from a known intermediary, such as is the case with TRESIMA in Slovakia.

Increasing response rates

Our approach to increasing recruitment will draw on theories of social exchange for increasing survey response as introduced to survey design methods, where the likelihood of responding, and doing so accurately, is increased when perceived benefits outweigh costs (Dillman, 2012). In line with key recommendations, we will incorporate the following design choices:

- Ensuring that it is convenient for the participant to respond,
- Reducing survey length,
- Designing the survey in a respondent-friendly manner,
- Asking interesting questions,
- Reducing complexity by asking only what is absolutely necessary,
- Minimising requests for personal or sensitive information.

Drawing further on Dillman's recommendations, we will encourage response by asking for assistance, by emphasising how individual contributions will be more broadly beneficial, and by stressing that opportunities to respond are limited. Moreover, respondents can indicate at the end of the questionnaire whether they want to remain updated about the results of the employer study. Each subsequent communication will contain new information to encourage interest.

Further, we will acknowledge the role of trust in facilitating response, with a commitment to ensuring stated benefits are upheld. Therefore, each local data collection team will give due consideration to preparing a Data Information Sheet that outlines the purpose of the employer study and explains how, where and how long respondent's data will be retained. This Data Information Sheet will also include contact details in case respondents have additional questions or concerns. LISER will prepare a draft of such a Data Information Sheet which can be adapted by the data collection teams to their local context.

Although they are shown to increase response, it is not possible to offer incentives given budget constraints. However, it is anticipated that the nature of the survey content will in itself incentivise companies to respond. The outcomes at each contact attempt will be recorded for each sample member. Response rates will be calculated using AAPOR standard typology for final disposition codes (AAPOR, 2023).

Company dashboards

One important incentive for employers to complete the survey is the possibility of viewing aggregate results and comparing with other companies in the same or other sectors. The main characteristics may include:

- *Current use of RWA*: percentage of employees working remotely by different frequencies (e.g., 0-5%, 5-20%, 21-40%, 41-60%, 61-80%, 81-100%) and a graphical representation of current RWA usage.
- *Expected use of RWA in 5 years*: estimate the proportion of employees who will telework at different frequencies in 5 years and a graphical representation of the expected use of RWAs.
- *Perception of productivity effects of RWA*: views on productivity, creativity, and satisfaction of remote vs. on-site employees, and a graphical representation of opinions (e.g., bar chart for different levels of productivity, creativity, and satisfaction).
- *Perception of potential positive effects of RWA*: perceived benefits of telework by firm (e.g., larger talent pool, higher retention, higher productivity), and a graphical representation of the various benefits.
- *Perception of potential negative effects of RWA*: perceived disadvantages of teleworking by company (e.g., fewer opportunities for supervision, more difficult to coordinate, less communication), and a graphical representation of the various disadvantages.
- *Use of digital technologies and technical support for RWA*: use of digital technologies in companies (e.g., remote access to company networks, CRM software, collaboration tools), and a graphical representation of the use of different technologies.
- *Difficulties to hire*: the main reasons for difficulties in recruiting staff with higher education and vocational training, and a graphical representation of the reasons for recruitment difficulties.

Additional recruitment campaigns as a back-up plan

If responses from our stratified sampling explained earlier prove too low (despite sending reminders), a back-up plan is provided based on additional recruitment campaigns and convenience sampling. WP8 will support this convenience sampling through promotional activities. The following sub-sections provide additional details specific to each country on how to raise awareness regarding the employer survey.

Finland

Table 15: Additional survey promotion channels for Finland

Stakeholder promotion channels or dedicated outreach event	Short description of how the channel is expected to contribute to the achievement of the estimated sample (scope of the channel)	Target group description
The Regional council of South Savo	Representatives of the municipalities will be contacted and asked to share our employer survey with the employers in the region	Companies in the South Savo region
Etelä-Savon Yrittäjät (regional entrepreneurs' network)	Representatives of the entrepreneurs' network will be contacted and asked to share our employer survey with their members	Entrepreneurs in the South Savo region
Miksei Mikkeli (Mikkeli employers' network)	Representatives of the employers' network will be contacted and asked to share our employer survey with their members	Companies in the Mikkeli region
Large organisations	Representatives of large organisations which have many remote workers and satellite offices in South Savo like OP Financial Group will be contacted by email	Companies with many remote workers and satellite offices in South Savo
Finnish Startup Community	Representatives of the network will be contacted by email	More than 200 Finnish growth companies and startups
Employer chamber of commerce	Representatives of the employers' network will be contacted and asked to share our employer survey with their members	Companies in both Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo

Germany

In Germany, it will be more cost-effective to draw an additional sample of employers that will be contacted via email.

Luxembourg

Table 16: Additional survey promotion channels for Luxembourg

Stakeholder promotion channels or dedicated outreach event	Short description of how the channel is expected to contribute to the achievement of the estimated sample (scope of the channel)	Target group description
Chamber of Industry and Commerce	Representatives of Chamber of Industry and Commerce's will be contacted by email	Employers in selected sectors
Employer's union	Representatives of employer's union will be contacted and asked to share our employer survey with their members	Employers in selected sectors
Companies with satellite offices	Representatives of companies with satellite offices like Deloitte, KPMG, and PwC will be contacted by email	Companies with satellite office
Eivilux	Organiser of the HR Lux Trade Fair (next one is unfortunately on 20 March 2025). We will contact them by email and ask to share our employer survey with their members	Employers in selected sectors

Portugal

In Portugal it will be more cost-effective to approach employers through survey/marketing companies.

Slovakia

Table 17: Additional survey promotion channels for Slovakia

Stakeholder promotion channels or dedicated outreach event	Short description of how the channel is expected to contribute to the achievement of the estimated sample (scope of the channel)	Target group description
Slovak Chamber of Commerce and Industry	Representatives of the chamber will be approached via contacts available on the official web site: https://www.sopk.sk	Employers in selected sectors
Association of employer unions of Slovakia unions	Representatives of the association will be approached via contacts available on the official web site: https://www.azzz.sk/	Employers in selected sectors
Association of Research and Development Industrial Organisations	Channels will allow to approach member organisations of the association. We will directly approach general secretary of the association Assoc. Prof. Juraj Wagner (zpvvo@zpvvo.sk).	Research and industrial development employers
Cooperating with employers of the Faculty of National Economy of the University of	Trexima Bratislava cooperates with the University of Economics, which has concluded cooperation with several major employers in the country. We will therefore also send a request for cooperation in the questionnaire collection to this university.	Employers in selected sectors

Economics in Bratislava		
HRcomm & SME conference	HRCOMM https://www.hrcomm.sk/aktivita/kalendar-podujati/nase-podujatia/hrcomm-sme-konferencia	HR department workers

2.2.4. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Below is summarised the eligibility for the employer survey:

Inclusion criteria

- Companies with 5 or more employees, stratified by sector and company size,
- Only companies located in Finland, Germany, Luxembourg, Portugal, Slovakia.

Exclusion criteria

- Companies with less than 5 employees,
- Self-employed businesses.

2.3. Survey content and structure

This section describes the general structure and the logic behind the main building blocks of the employer survey, and how each block aims to address the research hypotheses listed in section 2.1.1. The survey will include the following eight broad sections: Structural variables, RWA usage and perception, Organisational practices for RWA and general working conditions, Concerns about skills shortage, Concerns about health and safety of workers, Willingness to pay for remote work, Locational strategies, and Participant characteristics. The table below (Table 18) provides an overview of the planned detailed questionnaire, to be completed as part of task T3.2 at most 2 months after this deliverable.

Table 18: Rationale and examples of questionnaire items per survey section

Section	Description	Rationale (relevant for research tasks)	Example concepts and questionnaire items
Structural variables	A set of objective basic firm characteristics needed as control variables in our analyses in WP4	Industry sector, company size, age, and gender structure, as well as location are needed as independent variables for the analysis, but also for comparability between case study locations. These are relevant for all research tasks T4.1-T4.6, T6.1 and T6.3.	<i>Approximately how many employees are currently on your company's payroll? What is the ZIP code of the location of your establishment?</i>

RWA usage and perception	A set of questions about the current and future (within 5 years) remote work policy as well as their perception of positive and negative aspects of remote work, including productivity	This section aims to understand the current and future role of remote work in the company culture and strategy, including employers' perception of the positive or negative effects of RWA. These are relevant for all research tasks T4.1-T4.6, T6.1 and T6.3.	<i>Please estimate the share of your employees who currently work remotely Please estimate the share of your employees whose primary job tasks could at least to some extent be performed remotely From your perspective, what are the advantages of RWA?</i>
Organisational practices for RWA and general working conditions	A set of questions about the organisational support to remote work (e.g., 'telework package'), but also general working conditions that could influence the organisation support to RWA such as importance of teamwork, flexibility in working time, training programme, number of hierarchy levels, and monitoring policy	<i>This section develops in more detail company structural variables with a view of creating a typology of employers and their level of support for RWA. Questions in this section are inspired from the UK Workplace Employment Relations Study (WERS) and are necessary to compare results with previous surveys. This section aims to address research tasks T4.1 and T4.3.</i>	<i>To what extent did you change the following practices to accommodate remote working ...? Decreased, Unchanged, Increased Frequency of communication or consultation with employees Team working Size, organisation of office spaces (e.g. desk sharing, no fixed desk) Working time flexibility Minimum requirements for on-site presence Training practices (frequency and/or topics variety) Performance pay or fringe benefits Monitoring tools to supervise employees Frequency of feedback on employees' performance Number of selection criteria Number of employee retention actions</i>
Concerns about skills shortage	A set of questions about qualification of recent vacancies, difficulties to hire, and to which extent RWA could be a solution for this	This section specially aims to address research task T4.4.	<i>Has the use of RWA helped your company to reduce skill shortages of qualified employees over the last 5 years?</i>
Concerns about health and safety of workers	A set of questions on company policy on mental health including burnout and sick leave	This section aims to address research task T4.2.	<i>Approximately, what proportion of employees in your company have experienced a burnout/burnout-related work absence in the last three years?</i>
Willingness to pay for remote work	A vignette study about the employer's salary offers to hypothetical candidates with different	This section aims to address research tasks T4.4 and T4.5.	Respondents are shown a series of vignettes describing hypothetical choices between job

2.5. Expected outcomes

The expected output of this study is:

- A dataset that will enable to test research hypothesis and investigate research questions presented in **Table 2**,
- Information derived from the Employer Dataset that will complement data sources used to forecasts RWA trends in T6.1 and inform modelling of travel behaviour patterns in T6.2,
- An open dataset (employer survey dataset #7) that will be prepared at later stages of the WW4WL (see D1.2 Data management plan),
- Information that will be fed into a dashboard for employers to provide useful insights back to the participants and other stakeholders in a user-friendly way (T3.5),
- A series of articles in scientific journals presenting the findings and conclusions derived from analysis of collected data (T8.2).

2.6. Expected scientific and social benefits

Scientific benefits of the employer study consist of gaining new insights into RWA economic impacts from the employer's perspective (**Table 2**). This way, WW4WL will help to employers utilize more efficiently the benefits of RWA (e.g., expand the talent pool, save costs, and help employers in addressing some of the concerns linked to RWA such as a lack of team cohesion, maintaining company culture, and managing time zone and regional, cultural differences. Companies will better understand for which types of workers which level of RWA is optimal and how to define the future of telework compensation or packages.

3. Protocol for the employee study

3.1. Aim

The main objective of WP5 on the ‘employee perspective’ is to enhance the understanding of the socio-economic impacts of RWAs by focusing on the private sphere. There is today a lot of ambiguity about RWA from an employee’s perspective as well, and therefore a need to gain more insights into how employees think about RWA.

The employee study is based on (i) an online survey collecting data on the employees’ views and practices regarding RWA, (ii) a time diary in which employees report how they spend their time during a day working at the office and a day working remotely, and (iii) in-depth interviews discussing household arrangements. In each of these three, differences between employees in terms of age, gender and location (urban/rural) will be made explicit. Because the data will be collected in five different countries with different labour markets and welfare systems, the study also aims to reveal the role of cultural differences.

3.1.1. Research hypotheses

The WW4WL project has limited the employee research scope to five key topic areas that will be further explored in five separate tasks within WP5. Similar to the employer survey, each of these five topic areas refer to a specific research hypothesis, partly based on insights obtained during the literature review in WP2, partly based on previous research by consortium partners on these topics. The way the hypotheses are formulated makes clear which variables are important for the WP5 analysis, which in turn serves to guide the types of questions asked in the survey (**Table 20**). For each of these five topics, we also hypothesize that results will differ across culture (five survey countries) and by location (urban/rural). Location information is especially pertinent for integrating into the land use and transport models in WP6. In other words, the diversity related to the employee’s home and workplace environment is a cross-cutting theme throughout the five topic areas. **Table 20** provides an overview of the research hypotheses, and which analytical methods will be used for which task and topic area.

Table 20: Research hypotheses and research questions from the employee perspective

Task	Topic area	Research hypothesis (RH)	Main research question(s)	Main analytical methods
T5.1	Quality of life and quality of time	RH 5.1: Differences in the impacts of RWA on quality of life (work-life balance and loneliness) and quality of time according to employees’ socio-demographic characteristics and country-specific factors. It	What are the profiles of employees? What are the relationship between the intensity of RWA and quality of life and quality of time? Does these relationship vary according to the socio-	Sequencing, Factor analysis (e.g., PCA) and cluster analysis, Qualitative analysis, Multivariate techniques

		provides a basis for a typology of employee profile.	demographic characteristics of employees and the specific characteristics of the country in which they work?	
T5.2	Productivity, creativity, mental health and loneliness	RH5.2: Differences in the impact of RWA on employee productivity, creativity and mental health, and loneliness depending on the typology of employee profile and the typology of company friendliness to RWA profile in which they work.	Which profiles of employees and companies benefit most from teleworking in terms of productivity, creativity, mental health and loneliness? Are there gender differences?	Standard econometric methods, Qualitative analysis
T5.3	Digital skills divide	RH5.3: Using digital tools when remotely working may help to reduce the digital skills divide .	Does the RWA intensity have the potential to narrow the digital skills divide? What is the most effective use of digital tools to bridge the digital skills divide? Are there socio-demographic differences?	Standard econometric methods
T5.4	Willingness to change household and workplace locations	RH5.4: RWA, in conjunction with a range of other factors including the attributes of the residence, the job, the employment area, and the commuting requirements, might play a significant role in influencing the decision of employees regarding their place of residence and employment .	Does RWA impact employees' willingness to relocate teleworkers' residences and/or employment?	Discrete choice models
T5.5	Taxation and social security implications	RH5.5: The RWA tax and social security legislations might impact on household incomes in border areas.	What is the potential impact of international regulations governing RWA (tax and social security legislations) on the incomes of households living in a cross-border area?	Simulation, Qualitative analysis
T6.1 (with input from T5.1)	RWA uptake and wage distributions (employee perspective)	RH6.1: Uptake of RWA will differ by country, sector, location (urban/rural), and gender. This will also have	What are the effects of RWA on wage distribution?	Spatial modelling

		implications for wage distribution across different segments of the labour market.		
T6.2	Mobility impacts	RH6.2: RWA affects out-of-home activities and travel behaviour of employees potentially leading to unintended and rebound effects.	What are the effects of RWA on out-of-home activities and travel behaviour?	Transport Modelling
T6.3 (with input from T5.4)	Spatial impacts	RH6.3: RWA impacts household and workplace relocation	What are the effects of RWA on space?	Spatial modelling
T6.4 (with input from T6.2 and T6.3)	Additional health impacts	RH6.5: RWA impacts transport-related health impacts by affecting exposure to emissions , traffic injuries and noise	What are the effects of RWA on health and emissions?	Spatial modelling

The resultant analyses in WP5 will lead to a summary of the main socio-economic effects of RWA from an employee’s perspective (T5.6). It will detail a baseline that shows the business-as-usual projection. But it will also focus on how typologies of employees regarding remote work can evolve over time, the potential impact of remote work on quality of life and quality of time, interactions with company practices and regional context, the spatial impacts of remote work in terms of residential and workplace re-locations of households, and inequalities in terms of digital divide, location, and gender.

3.2. Study design

The employee study consists of (i) an employee survey, (ii) a time diary, and (iii) in-depth interviews.

Similar to the employer study, the **employee survey** will be conducted online (web and mobile) and will be run using the MOTUS platform. We will again develop a survey instrument that is adaptable to different national contexts of the five case studies (i.e. Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo region in Finland, Munich Metropolitan Area in Germany, Greater Region of Luxembourg, Lisbon Metropolitan Area, cities of Bratislava, Zilina, Kosice, and rural areas in Slovakia). Screening questions at the start of the survey will ensure that only the targeted study population of these case study areas participate in the survey. The questionnaire will be available in the following languages: English, Finnish, French, German, Portuguese, and Slovak. LISER will coordinate the design of the questionnaire in English. Local data collection teams will

be responsible for translation in their own languages: UH for Finnish, LISER for French, TUM for German, IST-ID for Portuguese, and UNIZA for Slovak. Survey questions will be developed in consultation with partners from across work packages. Similar to the employer survey, the employee survey design will be followed by four cycles of validation and tests. First, the survey questions will be **reviewed by experts** (e.g., from the advisory board members), primarily to validate the scope of the research questions matches what was committed in the grant agreement. Second, the resulting questionnaire will be implemented in the MOTUS platform and **tested for functionality and flow** by the design team. Third, a **formal pilot testing** will take place checking for the correct understanding of survey questions by native speakers in the five case studies following a think-aloud protocol. This cognitive test aims to confirm the correct understanding for each question in each language targeting a minimum of two or three respondents per location, or until saturation is reached (i.e. no more new feedback is reported by testers). These 'live' respondents will be selected to represent best the target sample i.e. employees not directly related to the project who sometimes work from home. This pilot test will be coordinated by LISER, with support from other data collection teams. Fourth and finally, a second larger pilot (with approx. 40 employees) will be run to test the validity of the data produced by the SP experiments. This second pilot is coordinated by IST-ID and will take place in all case study locations given that the formulation of the alternatives in the choice experiment might be case-dependent.

After finishing the employee survey, all respondents will be invited to participate in a second phase of data collection, i.e. **time diary**. Respondents will be invited to download the MOTUS time diary app, which is available for Apple and Android users. The target is that at least 40% of the respondents to the employee survey also participate in the MOTUS time diary. Participants will be asked to complete the time diary for one day they are working remotely (e.g., at home) and one day in-office. This **two-day** approach has the advantage that the time diary study is less burdensome for participants. There are, however, also some complexities, especially in terms of the assignment of days. This cannot be done randomly as in other time use studies because the aim is to have one day at the office and one day in an RWA. A way to work around this is to set up two-time diary studies in MOTUS: one for a workday at the office and one for a remote working day. However, such an approach must be thoroughly discussed technically with IT experts from hbits, which manages the data collection platform MOTUS. The time diaries will also contribute to assessing mobility behaviours and impacts in WP6 (T6.2 and T6.3) by means of a GPS logging of work and other discretionary trips during an office and a remote workday. The time diary questions will be designed in English by VUB. Local data collection teams will be responsible for translation in their own languages: UH for Finnish, LISER for French, TUM for German, IST-ID for Portuguese, and UNIZA for Slovak.

After finishing the time diary, selected users will be invited to participate in a follow-up **in-depth interview**, with a target of reaching at least 30 employees in each case study. To take into account different work-life arrangements, only employees

belonging to one of the following four profiles will be interviewed: (i) employees living in dual-earner couples with children, (ii) employees living in dual-earner couples without children, (iii) employees who live alone with children, and (iv) employees who live alone without children. EPFL will prepare an interview grid, and interviews (in-person or online) will be organised and recorded by the local data collection teams. Audio recordings will be transcribed and translated by the local data collection teams using AI tools such as NVivo, Otter.ai, Rev, Sonix, Trint, Descript, Happy Scribe. Translated transcripts will then be analysed for its content by EPFL. More information about the data management process of the interviews can be found in D1.2 *Data management plan*.

3.2.1. Study population

The study population consists of employees **20 years of age and above** who are employed at the time of the survey. The study population aims for a matching proportion of company sizes (for all sectors) from the employer survey. The collection campaigns also need to include representative sample in terms of socio-demographic characteristics and at the same time ensure a minimum quota of remote workers and non-remote workers.

3.2.2. Sampling frame

Sampling criteria: Because of budgetary limitations and the lack of adequate sampling sources, we are not able to do a stratified sampling of employees. Instead, data collection teams will use convenience sampling. In doing so, the data collection managers will monitor the extent to which the obtained sample during the data collection phase of the employee survey and time diary follows the population distribution in terms of age, gender, and location. For the employee study, the geographical scale is the case study by default. This means: Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo region for Finland, Munich Metropolitan Area for Germany, Greater Region of Luxembourg, Lisbon Metropolitan Area for Portugal and the cities of Bratislava, Zilina, and Kosice and its rural area for Slovakia.

Target sample size of the employee survey is 1,000 respondents per case study. At least 40% of these respondents will also participate in the MOTUS time diary. This means at least 400 respondents per case study. Finally, at least 30 of these MOTUS users will also participate in the in-depth interviews. Tables 21 to 35 specify target numbers per case study for the employee survey as well as the time diary per age group, gender, and location. Such target numbers are not specified for the in-depth interviews as this is a qualitative research phase.

Weighting: Convenience sampling has its strengths and weaknesses (Lehdonvirta et al., 2021). Strengths refer to the rapid method to recruit survey participants, but weaknesses refer to topical and economic self-selection that induces differences between the sample and the studied population. There is a higher risk for obtaining an unbalanced and non-representative sample in the employee survey and time diary. As with the employer survey, we will therefore calculate weights in the post data

collection phase. The weights at the employee level ensure that the distributions by, for example, age classes, gender, and a number of resident or a cross-border workers (in case of cross-bordering labour markets in the case study of the Grand Region of Luxembourg) are representative of the population at work in each case study.

Finland

The case study area in Finland encompasses Helsinki metropolitan area and South Savo region. The Helsinki metropolitan area consists of the capital city Helsinki as well as Espoo, Vantaa, and Kauniainen. The area has a population of around 1.25 million and it is by far the most urbanised and economically important region in Finland. In contrast, the South Savo region has a population of around 150,000, with 12 municipalities of which only three have a status of a city. However, located at the heart of the Finnish lake district, South Savo is a popular summer cabin location for the Finns, and thus it is an important remote work region especially during the summer.

Table 21: Stratification of employees in Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo by age group

Age group	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
	Helsinki Metropolitan Area / South Savo			
20-29 Early career	199,285 / 13,635	20.1 / 12.3	100 / 50	50 / 15
30-44 Mid-career	300,487 / 19,574	30.3 / 17.6	250 / 100	100 / 35
45-59 Late-career	224,474 / 24,058	22.6 / 21.7	250 / 100	100 / 35
60+ Early retiring	268,281 / 53,809	27.0 / 48.4	100 / 50	50 / 15
Target	992,527 / 111,076	100 / 100	700 / 300 = 1000	300 / 100 = 400

Sources used to collect statistical data: STATISTICS FINLAND

https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin__vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11rf.px/

Table 22: Stratification of employees in Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo by gender

Gender	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
	Helsinki Metropolitan Area / South Savo			
Man	478,530 / 54,593	48.2 / 49.1	350 / 150	150 / 50
Woman	513,997 / 56,483	51.8 / 50.9	350 / 150	150 / 50
Target	992,527 / 111,076	100 / 100	700 / 300 = 1000	300 / 100 = 400

Sources used to collect statistical data: STATISTICS FINLAND

https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin__vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11rf.px/

Table 23: Stratification of employees in Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo by location

Location	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
South Savo region	111,076	10.1	300	100
e.g. Mikkeli	43,308	3.9	90	30
e.g. Savonlinna	14,658	1.3	90	30
e.g. Pieksämäki	27,607	2.5	60	20
other municipalities in South Savo	25,503	2.3	60	20
Helsinki Metropolitan Area	992,527	89.9	700	300
Espoo	238,609	2.6	200	90
Helsinki	551,748	50.0	350	150
Kauniainen	7,982	0.7	-	-
Vantaa	194,188	17.6	150	60
Target	1,103,603	100	1000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: STATISTICS FINLAND

https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/StatFin_vaerak/statfin_vaerak_pxt_11rf.px/

Germany

The employee survey in the German case study will be focused on the Munich Metropolitan Area. This study area comprises Munich, the neighboring cities of Augsburg, Ingolstadt, Landshut and Rosenheim, and the municipality with high commuter flows to any of the cities. This metropolitan region functions as a polycentric structure, where Munich is the center city.

Table 24: Stratification of employees in Germany by age group

Age group	Germany population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
15 - 25	3,364,784	9.7	100	40
25 - 35	7,630,188	22.1	225	90
35 - 45	7,757,927	22.5	225	90
45-55	7,731,163	22.4	225	90
55 or more	7,975,577	23.2	225	90
Target	41,934,876	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: German Statistical Office, national values, 31.12.2022. N.B.: For Germany, it was decided to keep the age groups in 10-year intervals, in line with the original census strata and scale instead of interpolating the values to the study area specifically and to the age brackets used by other countries. Linear interpolations can be done to scale and fit the age brackets for Munich.

Table 25: Stratification of employees in Munich Metropolitan Area by gender

Gender	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Male	1,176,206	53.4	500	200
Female	1,025,081	46.6	500	200
Target	2,201,287	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: Bavarian Statistical Office, municipality values aggregated to the Munich metropolitan area. 31.12.2022.

Table 26: Stratification of employees in Munich Metropolitan Area by location

Location	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Urban municipality	1,881,289	85.5	850	340
Rural municipality	319,998	14.5	150	60
Target	2,201,287	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: Bavarian Statistical Office, municipality values aggregated to the Munich metropolitan area. 31.12.2022.

Luxembourg

The employee survey in the Luxembourgish case study will be focused on The Great Duchy of Luxembourg and its cross-bordering regions in Belgium, France, and Germany.

Table 27: Stratification of employees in the Greater Region of Luxembourg by age group

Age group	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
20-29 Early career	80,240	16.5	165	66
30-44 Mid-career	208,470	42.9	429	172
45-59 Late-career	176,190	36.3	363	145
60+ Early retiring	21,140	4.3	43	17
Target	486,040	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: (Tableaux interactifs relatifs aux stocks d'emplois - Le marché de l'emploi - ADEM - FACILITONS L'EMPLOI - Luxembourg (public.lu)) - Field: Employees and civil servants (self-employed are excluded) Date : 03.31.2023

Table 28: Stratification of employees in the Greater Region of Luxembourg by gender

Gender	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Man	286,500	58.9	590	236
Woman	199,540	41.1	410	164
Target	486,040	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: ([Tableaux interactifs relatifs aux stocks d'emplois - Le marché de l'emploi - ADEM - FACILITONS L'EMPLOI - Luxembourg \(public.lu\)](#)) Field: Employees and civil servants (self-employed are excluded). Date: 03.31.2023

Table 29: Stratification of employees in the Greater Region of Luxembourg by location

Location	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Luxembourg	264,290	54.4	544	218
Belgium	50,930	10.5	105	42
France	119,110	24.5	245	98
Germany	51,710	10.6	106	42
Target	486,040	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: ([Tableaux interactifs relatifs aux stocks d'emplois - Le marché de l'emploi - ADEM - FACILITONS L'EMPLOI - Luxembourg \(public.lu\)](#)). Field: Employees and civil servants (self-employed are excluded). Date: 03.31.2023

Portugal

The employee survey in the Portuguese case study will be focused on the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. This study area comprises the municipalities of Alcochete, Almada, Amadora, Barreiro, Cascais, Lisboa, Loures, Mafra, Moita, Montijo, Odivelas, Oeiras, Palmela, Sesimbra, Seixal, Setúbal, Sintra, and Vila Franca de Xira.

Table 30: Stratification of employees in Lisbon Metropolitan Area by age group

Age group	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
20-29 Early career	163,907	13.4	134	54
30-44 Mid-career	462,607	37.8	378	151
45-59 Late career	447,005	36.6	368	146
60+ Early retiring	148,744	12.2	122	49
Target	1,222,263	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: <https://www.ine.pt/>; <https://www.pordata.pt/>

Table 31: Stratification of employees in Lisbon Metropolitan Area by gender

Gender	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Male	5,983,558	49%	490	1956
Female	623,908	51%	510	204
Target	1,222,263	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: <https://www.ine.pt/>; <https://www.pordata.pt/>

Table 32: Stratification of employees in Lisbon Metropolitan Area by location

Location	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Lisbon	234,530	19.2	192	77
Peninsula Setubal	331,798	27.2	271	108
Greater Lisbon (without Lisbon)	655,935	53.7	537	215
Target	1,222,263	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: <https://www.ine.pt/>; <https://www.pordata.pt/>

Slovakia

Slovakia is a small and well-connected country, with the two largest cities of Bratislava (west) and Kosice (east) only about 420km from each other, and Zilina almost equidistant between the two (north). Bratislava is the capital, as well as Slovakia's economic, business, and cultural centre. Its proximity to Vienna and Budapest also makes it particularly attractive for employment. Compared to the rest of the country, salaries are generally higher in Bratislava (by 12-15%), which is compensated by a slightly higher cost of living (10-20%) and by significantly higher property costs (25-80%, depending on size and location). The employee survey focus will therefore be on various patterns of remote work between these three cities and residents of other towns and villages. In **Table 33** and **Table 34**, we considered economically active inhabitants. However, we could not identify a similar data for **Table 35** and therefore we considered the entire population.

Table 33: Stratification of employees in Slovakia by age group

Age group	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
20-29 Early career	394,100	14.2	142	57
30-44 Mid-career	1,125,300	40.4	404	162
45-59 Late career	1,024,900	36.8	368	147
60+ Early retiring	238,500	8.6	86	34
Target	2,782,800	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: Economically active population by age groups and sex, 2023, 4Q.: <https://data.statistics.sk/api>. Notes: in Slovakia we usually use 5 years categories to monitor salary changes, but 15 years gap and 4 age groups are good suggested distinctions. However, we cannot conflate age with seniority.

Table 34: Stratification of employees in Slovakia by gender

Gender	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Female	1,307,000	47.0	470	190
Male	1,475,600	53.0	530	210
Target	2,782,600	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: Economically active population by age groups and sex, 2023, 4Q.: <https://data.statistics.sk/api>

Table 35: Stratification of employees in Slovakia by location

Location	Study area population (national statistics)	Population share (%)	Target sample employee survey	Target sample time diary
Bratislava functional urban area	723,714	13.3%	150	60
Zilina	161,052	3.0%	50	40
Kosice functional urban area / agglomeration	356,695	6.6%	70	40
Other – urban (Presov, Nitra, Trnava, Trencin, Banska Bystrica)	691,343	12.7%	130	60
Other (rural and smaller cities)	3,501,908	64.4%	600	200
Target	5,434,712	100	1,000	400

Sources used to collect statistical data: Population of Slovakia and of SK cities: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/URB_LPOP1/default/table?lang=en

3.2.3. Recruitment strategy

The employee data collection will take two approaches:

- 1) companies from the employer survey that have given their consent to be contacted again will be asked to distribute the employee survey to their employees, and
- 2) a communication campaign to reach employees independently from their employer, via social media and stakeholder promotion channels (see per country details below).

Each step in the data collection of the employee study (i.e. employee survey, time diaries, and in-depth interviews) will last for two months.

Finland

Table 36: Promotion channels for employee recruitment in Helsinki Metropolitan Area and South Savo

Stakeholder promotion channel / Social media campaign / Dedicated outreach events	Short description of how the channel or the event is expected to contribute to the achievement of the estimated sample (scope of the channel)	Target group
Email to stakeholders	Invitation email to Finnish stakeholders in the project's Stakeholder Panel so they distribute the survey to their employees and/or members they represent	Employees from government representatives, big companies, medium-sized companies, representatives of cities and rural areas
Etelä-Savon Yrittäjät (regional entrepreneurs' network)	Invitation email to members so they distribute the survey to their employees	Employees in the South Savo region
Miksei Mikkeli (Mikkeli employers' network)	Invitation email to members so they distribute the survey to their employees	Employees in the Mikkeli region
Large organisations	Invitation email to members so they distribute the survey to their employees	Employees of organisations that have employees working remotely in South Savo
Finnish Startup Community	Invitation email to members so they distribute the survey to their employees	Employees of growth companies and startups that have employees working remotely in South Savo

Germany

Table 37: Promotion channels for employee recruitment in Munich Metropolitan Area

Stakeholder promotion channel / Social media campaign / Dedicated outreach events	Short description of how the channel or the event is expected to contribute to the achievement of the estimated sample (scope of the channel)	Target group
Email to stakeholders	Invitation email to German stakeholders in the project's Stakeholder Panel so they distribute the survey to their employees and/or members they represent	Employees from government representatives, big companies, medium-sized companies, representatives of cities and rural areas
Email to TUM management	Invitation email to TUM employees	TUM staff
LinkedIn	Sharing posts about employee data collection using TUM Travel Behavior LinkedIn profile	Researchers, young professionals

Luxembourg

Table 38: Promotion channels for employee recruitment in the Greater Region of Luxembourg

Stakeholder promotion channel / Social media campaign / Dedicated outreach events	Short description of how the channel or the event is expected to contribute to the achievement of the estimated sample (scope of the channel)	Target group
Email to stakeholders	Invitation email to Luxembourg stakeholders in the project's Stakeholder Panel so they distribute the survey to their employees and/or members they represent	Employees from government representatives, big companies, medium-sized companies, representatives of cities, and rural areas
Labour union	Representatives of labour unions like OGBL and ALEBA will be contacted by email asking to promote the employee survey among their members	Employees from different sectors working in Luxembourg
Facebook	Campaign through LISER social media	Employed residents and cross-border workers in Luxembourg
X	Information posted on the platform	Employed residents and cross-border workers in Luxembourg
LinkedIn	Sharing posts about employee data collection using LISER LinkedIn profile	Employees in selected sectors Employed residents and cross-border workers in Luxembourg
LISER web site	Starting with a press release and a general announcement on the LISER website and social media, followed by paid social media campaign on Facebook and X.	Employed residents and cross-border workers in Luxembourg

Portugal

In Portugal it will be more cost-effective to approach employees through survey/marketing companies.

Slovakia

Table 39: Promotion channels for employee recruitment in Slovakia

Stakeholder promotion channel / Social media campaign / Dedicated outreach events	Short description of how the channel or the event is expected to contribute to the achievement of the estimated sample (scope of the channel)	Target group
Email to stakeholders	Invitation email to Slovak stakeholders in the project's Stakeholder Panel so they distribute the survey to their employees and/or members they represent	Employees from government representatives, big companies, medium-sized companies, representatives of cities, and rural areas
Confederation of Trade Unions of the Slovak Republic	Representatives of the confederation will be approached via contacts available on the official web site: https://www.kozsr.sk	Employees approached by their trade union representatives

HR organisations e.g. HRCOMM	HR workers will be asked to approach employees in their organisation	Employees approached by their HR department
Zilina IT cluster	Managers of member IT companies will be approached with the request to ask they employees to participate in the survey	Employees of IT companies located in the Zilina region
Contact to companies UNIZA already collaborates with e.g. Siemens Healthineers, Kros, Brain:IT, Descartes, DXC Technology, Fuergy, Scheidt&Bachmann, Technia, Slovanet, Softec, Unicorn, Ipesoft, Stredoslovenská distribučná, Schaeffler, Onsemi, GoodRequest, Robe	UNIZA faculties have close collaboration with companies employing UNIZA graduates (e.g. invited lectures by industry partners, representatives of industry have one seat in each study program board, etc.). Deans of UNIZA faculties will be approached with the request to ask company managers to send the invitation to their employees	Employees of IT companies located in the Zilina region
UNIZA alumnis	Some of the UNIZA faculties have alumni organisations. Representatives for those organisations will be approached with the request to forward invitation to employee survey to UNIZA alumni	UNIZA alumni
UNIZA and other universities	UNIZA is in active contact with other Slovak universities (membership in national organisations, joint projects, etc.). UNIZA management will be approached to with the request to ask management of other Slovak universities to invite their employees to take part in the Employee survey	Employees of other Slovak universities
Facebook	social media campaign using UNIZA Facebook channel	Employees in selected sectors
LinkedIn	Sharing posts about employee data collection using university and faculties LinkedIn profiles	Employees in selected sectors

Increasing response rates

We use the same principles for the design of the employee survey and time diary as for the employer survey. Moreover, each case study has a budget to purchase non-financial incentives to encourage participation in the employee study.

Each case study has a budget of 5,000 EUR to organise a raffle with valuable prizes (e.g., equipment for remote work such as Wi-Fi routers and headphones, a goodie bag for remote workers including premium coffee beans, shopping and/or lunch vouchers) among the participants to the employee survey and time diary. Only participants that completed the first two phases of the employee study will be eligible for this raffle.

In addition, each case study has another budget of 1,500 EUR to purchase a non-financial incentive for each participant to the in-depth interviews (= 30 interviewees x 50 EUR).

3.2.4 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The employee study starts with the employee survey. Eligibility criteria for the employee survey are as follows:

- Inclusion criteria
 - Age: 20 years or older
 - Employment status: salaried employees
 - Location: only salaried employees located in one of the five case studies
 - Company size: minimum 5 employees
- Exclusion criteria
 - Age: 19 years or below
 - Employment status: everything except salaried employees

All respondents who participated in the employee survey will then be invited to the time diaries. No specific inclusion/exclusion criteria apply to the time diaries.

Finally, from the sample of the time diaries, 30 participants will be selected per case study who meet one of the four profiles specified in Section 3.2.

3.3. Employee survey content and structure

This section describes the general structure and the logic behind the main building blocks of the employee survey, and how each block aims to address the research hypotheses listed in section 3.1.1. The survey will include the following nine broad sections: Socio-demographic characteristics, Job characteristics, RWA usage and perception, Working conditions and Complementary organisational practices for RWA, Quality of time, Quality of life productivity and mental health, Digital use and digital skills, Current residential location (house & neighbourhood), Residential relocation & workplace change. The table below (**Table 40**) provides an overview of the planned detailed questionnaire, to be completed as part of task T3.2 at most 2 months after this deliverable.

Table 40: Rationale and examples of questionnaire items per survey section

Section	Description	Rationale (relevant for research tasks)	Example concepts and questionnaire items
Socio-demographic characteristics	A set of individual and household characteristics needed as control variables in our analyses in WP5.	Gender; Age; Level of education; Family situation are needed as independent variables for the analyses, but also for studying heterogeneity. These are relevant for all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What is the highest level of education you have completed?</i> • <i>What is your marital status?</i>

		research tasks of WP5, T6.1 and T6.3.	
Job characteristics	A set of job characteristics needed as control variables in our analyses in WP5.	Sector and Size of the firms; Occupation; Seniority; Employment status (e.g., contract) are needed as independent variables for the analyses in tasks T5.1 to T5.4.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What is approximately the size of your company?</i> • <i>What is your main occupation?</i>
RWA usage and perception	A set of questions about current use of RWA, perceptions of the benefits and drawbacks of RWA.	This section aims to identify the current use of RWA by employees, including, the intensity of RWA. These variables are needed as independent variables for the analysis of tasks T5.1 to T5.4; T6.1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Currently, how many times per week do you work outside of the office during regular working hours?</i> • <i>What difficulties do you encounter when working remotely?</i>
Working conditions and Complementary organisational practices for RWA	A set of questions on working conditions and organisational practices in place in the firm where employee works.	A broad range of working conditions and organisational practices (e.g., job security, skills development and training) will be captured in order to build the work sphere typology. This section aims to address research tasks T5.1 & T5.2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>When you start your work, can you usually predict when your working day will be over?</i> • <i>What is the size of the team (including yourself) in which you work (number of persons headed by the same person in charge or by yourself if you are in charge)?</i> • <i>In the past 12 months, have you undergone training related to your work, except any training obliged by law?</i>
Quality of time	A set of questions on quality of time including work-life balance and the division of household tasks.	This section aims to address research on T5.1 and used to build the private sphere typology used in T5.2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>To what extent are you satisfied with the division of housework between you and your partner?</i> • <i>Please rate how much you agree with the following statement: My work prevents me spending sufficient quality time with my family?</i>

Quality of life, productivity and mental health	A set of questions on employee well-being with a special focus on quality of life, mental health and productivity.	This section aims to address research on T5.1 and used to build the private sphere typology used in T5.2.	<i>To what extent to you agree with the following statement: My current work situation makes me feel more isolated from my coworkers? Compared to when you work in the office, when you work remotely (e.g., from home) your productivity is ... significantly lower / rather lower / about the same / rather higher / significantly higher?</i>
Digital use and digital skills	A set of questions on digital use and skills to examine the digital divide, highlighting the differences in usage depending on whether employee works at the office or remotely.	This section aims to address research task T5.3.	<i>Which of the following best describes your highest level of Information Communication Technology (ICT) skills? Do you use collaborative work tools ... more frequently in RWA / more frequently in the office / equally often at home and in the office</i>
Current residential location (house & neighbourhood)	A set of questions about the amenities of the place employees live and the level of satisfaction with them.	This section aims to address research task T5.4.	<i>In what type of dwelling do you live? To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement: in my neighbourhood there are insufficient public transit options nearby (bus, trains, tram, shared bike services)</i>
Residential relocation & workplace change	A stated preference study regarding the residential relocation and workplace change.	This section aims to address research task T5.4.	<i>Is your household planning to move in the next 2 years? Yes, Under consideration, but no definite plans at present, No</i>

3.4. Time diaries content and structure

For the WW4WL project, where the focus lies on working time in RWAs versus working time at the office as well as the impact hereof on non-working time, a distinction in the Online Activity Classification List (OACL) will be made between work activities (Section 3.4.1) and non-work activities (Section 3.4.2).

Each activity takes place within an activity context (Section 3.4.3). The temporal context of the activity is encapsulated in the registration in the time diary and includes:

1. **Duration.** The duration can be derived from the start and ending time of the activity (i.e., the activity episode).
2. **Timing.** The timing can be derived from the start time of the activity episode.
3. **Tempo.** The tempo or recurrence can be derived from the number of the same activity episodes over a time period.
4. **Sequence.** The sequence of activities can be derived from the series of activity episodes registered over a time period.

Additionally, spatial, social, digital, and emotional context can be inquired for each activity and includes, for example:

5. **Location.** The location captures where the activity took place.
6. **Mode of transport.** In case of a commute, the mode of transport can be questioned.
7. **Presence of others.** It can be questioned if someone was present and, if so, how the participant related to them.
8. **Digital device.** It can be asked if the participant used a digital device during the activity and, if so, what sort of device.
9. **Satisfaction.** On a scale from 0 to 10 a participants can be asked to rate their satisfaction with the activity.

Generally, questioning the context of the activity is assumed relevant, because the same lexicographic activity can get a different meaning depending on the context. For example, working in the morning might be more satisfying than working in the evening. Similarly, working from home in solitude might be interpreted as more productive compared to working from home while children are present.

A final contextual element to someone's time-use is the possibility to engage in more than one activity at the same time. For example, reading while having breakfast or eating while watching television.

10. **Secondary activity.** It is possible to add a second or parallel OACL to the time diary. In that case, and after registering their primary or main detailed activity, participants are asked if they did something else. The second or parallel OACL

can be presented in the same way as the primary or main OACL. The only difference being that it contains the activity “I did not do anything else” and does not ask context questions about the secondary or parallel detailed activity.

3.4.1. Work activities

In the population time use surveys, work activities are not registered in too much detail, because (i) large part of the population does not work and (ii) agencies conducting these surveys do not want participants to spend too much of their working time completing their time diaries (see, for example, Eurostat, 2020). So, typically work activities are subdivided into:

Paid work

- Doing paid work,
- Doing paid overtime,
- Doing unpaid overtime,
- Travelling as part of the job,
- Eating and drinking as part of the job,
- Doing small paid jobs,
- Doing paid internship, attending vocational education, studying during working hours,
- Doing a student job or other paid activities as a student,
- Helping someone of own household with paid work or farming,

Breaks

- Taking breaks during work,
- Waiting during work,
- Spending time at work before or after hours.

Not all these activities are relevant for the work-activity list used for the time diary study within the WW4WL project. The work-activity list thus needs further discussion within the project. In discussing the work-activity list, at least the following should be taken into consideration:

1. **Location of work.** Location is typically captured in the context question (see Section 2.3) but could also be part of the activity list to create space in the context questionnaire. Consider the following two examples.

Example 1. A participant registers doing paid work as an activity. The context questionnaire then asks whether paid work was done at home, at the office, at another location.

Example 2. A participant registers doing paid work at home as an activity. The context questionnaire then asks, for example, if paid work was done at home at a designated workplace (e.g., home office) or not.

2. **Type of work.** It might be relevant to distinguish different types of working activities, for example, distinguishing between online meetings, in-person meetings.
3. **Context of work.** Context questions can differ by activities (see Section 3.4.3). It might be relevant to ask specific context questions for work activities. For example, if at that time they would have preferred to work at the office or in a RWA.

All these decisions are dependent on the hypotheses to be tested and/or research questions to be answered within the WW4WL project and need careful consideration before being included in the time diary study.

3.4.2. Non-work activities

The inclusion of non-work activities in the OACL serves two purposes. First, it allows participants to register all their time-use for 24 hours. This increases the reliability of the data, because in the end all activity durations must sum up to 24 hours per day. This reduces biases, such as the social desirability bias or confirmation bias. Second, it allows to assess quality of time in terms of differences in time spent on non-working activities in function of how much working time is spent at the office or remotely. Additionally, it provides information about commuting time.

The decision on the non-work OACL mainly depends on two elements.

1. **Usability.** From a participants' point of view, the length and quality of the OACL is largely decisive in the success of the time-diary. A list that is too detailed and therefore too long, makes it hard for participants to see the forest from the trees. A list that is too little detailed, makes it hard for participants to decide under which detailed activity to classify how they have spent their time.
2. **Knowledge outcomes.** From a data analytical point of view, the detail of the OACL must be drawn up in such a way that it allows the proposed hypotheses to be tested or research questions to be answered.

It is recommended to find a non-work OACL in between the two listed examples.

3.4.3. Context questions

Although it is possible to attach a different context questionnaire to each different detailed activity, it is recommended to limit the number of different context questionnaires. Additionally, it is recommended to limit the number of questions. Within the light of the WW4WL project's objectives, it is advised to use different context questions for work-related non-travel activities, for non-work non-travel activities, and for travel activities. **Table 41** provides an overview of the most common context questionnaires. Note that for the sleep time typically no context is questioned.

Table 41: Overview most common context questionnaires

Non-work non-travel	
Question	Answers
Where were you?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> At home <input type="radio"/> In a second home/weekend home/holiday home/student room <input type="radio"/> At work or at school <input type="radio"/> At other people's home <input type="radio"/> In a restaurant/café/pub/... <input type="radio"/> In a shop/shopping centre/market/... <input type="radio"/> In a hotel/guesthouse/camp site/hostel/... <input type="radio"/> At another location
Were you alone or together with somebody you know?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Alone (or with unknown people) <input type="radio"/> In company
[[If in company]] Who were you with? Multiple answers possible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> With resident partner <input type="radio"/> With parent(s) living in the household <input type="radio"/> With child(ren) below 10 years of age living in the household <input type="radio"/> With other household members <input type="radio"/> With other persons that you know
Did you use a smartphone, tablet or computer for doing this?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
How satisfying was this activity to you?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Very unsatisfying <input type="radio"/> Unsatisfying <input type="radio"/> Neutral <input type="radio"/> Satisfying <input type="radio"/> Very satisfying
Travel	
Question	Answers
How did you travel? Multiple answers possible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> On foot <input type="radio"/> By bicycle or scooter (including electric) <input type="radio"/> By moped, motorcycle, motorbike, ... <input type="radio"/> By car as driver <input type="radio"/> By care as passenger <input type="radio"/> By taxi <input type="radio"/> By bus <input type="radio"/> By tram/metro/subway <input type="radio"/> By train <input type="radio"/> By airplane <input type="radio"/> By boat or ship

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o With another private transport o With another public transport
Were you alone or together with somebody you know?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Alone (or with unknown people) o In company
[[If in company]] Who were you with? Multiple answers possible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o With resident partner o With parent(s) living in the household o With child(ren) below 10 years of age living in the household o With other household members o With other persons that you know
Did you use a smartphone, tablet or computer for doing this?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Yes o No
How satisfying was this activity to you?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Very unsatisfying o Unsatisfying o Neutral o Satisfying o Very satisfying

Some context questionnaires distinguish between someone else being present (in the same room or house) and doing an activity WITH someone (e.g., cooking together or playing board games together). It still needs to be discussed if this type of distinction is also important for the WW4WL project.

3.4.4. Post-time diary questionnaire

After completing the time-diary phase and before finalizing the study for the participant, a small post-time diary questionnaire will be organised to provide additional context to the registered days. For example, it might make a difference if the remote working day from home is part of a weekly RWA, or just a form of flexibility that allowed someone to work from home on the day one of their children is home sick.

3.5. Content and structure of interviews

While the employee survey and time diary are important to gain insight into individual behaviour, it provides limited information on how this behaviour is influenced by the household context of which the individual is a part. The in-depth interview will therefore focus on how individuals experience daily rhythms and task arrangements in the household.

The interviews aim to cover all areas of daily life. In particular, the aim is to understand the implications of teleworking on both daily rhythms and arrangements. The questions in the interview grid cover several areas. The first area concerns the general perception of the rhythms of daily life. The second area relates to the perception of mobility and its meanings. The third area concerns the perception of time in the context of work. The fourth area explores the strategies people use to manage the

balance between their personal and professional lives. The fifth area concerns the teleworking policies proposed by companies. Finally, the last area aims to gain a better understanding of the way in which households equip themselves to cope with their daily lives, particularly in terms of the home and digital tools.

Table 42 shows a preliminary interview grid, prepared by EPFL and to be used by the local data collection teams in the five case studies.

Table 42: Preliminary interview grid

Question number	Question name
Theme 1: Perception of time in daily life	
Q1.1	Could you tell me about your daily rhythms?
Q1.2	Would you say that you sometimes feel overworked?
Q1.3	Do you sometimes feel you don't have enough time (children, work, house)?
Theme 2: Perception of daily mobility	
Q2.1	How would you describe your daily mobility?
Q2.2	Do you have any problems with your daily mobility?
Q2.3	How would you describe your travel times?
Theme 3: Perception of time at work	
Q3.1	Could you tell me about the intensity of your work
Q3.2	Do you sometimes feel overworked or tired at work?
Q3.3	Do you feel comfortable managing your working hours?
Theme 4: Time balance and conflicts and strategies	
Q4.1	Do you have any rules for dividing up the tasks of daily life in your household?
Q4.2	Can you describe the solutions you put in place to better manage the time in your daily life?
Q4.3	What would you like to change in your daily organisation?
Theme 5: Company policies	
Q5.1	Would you say that your company supports you in managing your day-to-day time?
Q5.2	Could you tell me what measures could improve the way you manage your daily time?
Q5.3	Do you have anything to add following our discussion?
Theme 6: Equipment	
Q6.1	Could you tell me about the equipment and devices that make it easier for you to manage your daily time?
Q6.2	Do you plan to acquire any new equipment to help you in your daily life?
Q6.3	What role does your smartphone play in communication within your household? Do you use a specific application to organise your personal and family life?

3.6. Contribution of Work Package partners

This section is to make explicit the various tasks related to getting started with the data collection campaigns in M10 (November 2024). Overall, UNIZA will lead the campaigns. LISER will lead the design of the employee questionnaire, VUB the time diary, and EPFL the in-depth interviews. Other WW4WL partners will contribute as outlined in **Table 43**. Below is a timeline of remaining activities before the launch of the data collection campaigns. For the employee study, this consists of **reviewing, testing and launching three types of data collection in three overlapping phases**: the employee survey, followed by the time diary, and finally the in-depth interviews:

1. (July-August 2024) Design and review in detail the interaction between the survey, the diaries, and the SP survey, e.g.:
 - a. questions needed for SPs e.g. residential preferences,
 - b. decide where to put questions about quality of time e.g. time diary vs survey,
 - c. modularising the (long) employee survey,
2. (August 2024) Time diary: decide on typology of work activities that can be comparable between type of jobs and case studies, relevant for making assessments on productivity, mental health, and quality of life,
3. (August-October 2024) Employee survey: expert review, revisions, and rounds of testing,
4. (September 2024) Review by Ethics committee, translations,
5. (November 2024) Launch of the employee survey.

Time diary will start in Spring 2025 (to avoid winter) and will be followed by the in-depth interviews.

Table 43: Timeline of activities before the launch of the data collection campaigns

ACTIVITY	Coordi- nation	START	DURATION (Weeks)	Week																																									
				27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51																	
				July							August							September							October							November							Dec						
Design employee study (survey + time use diary + interviews) in English	LISER	27	7	█																																									
Expert review: setting up the committee and include members of the advisory board	LISER	33	1								█																																		
Coordinate the expert review	LISER	34	2								█																																		
Revision of the questionnaire based on expert feedback	LISER	36	1															█																											
Submission to Institutional Research Ethics Committee	LISER	37	5															█																											
Implementation of employee questionnaire and time use diaries (English version) in MOTUS	LISER	37	3															█																											
Translations of employee study (survey + time use diary + interview questions, paper-based version)	LISER	38	2															█																											
Pilot testing: cognitive testing and sense check using think-aloud protocol for survey and time use diaries (all languages)	LISER	40	3															█																											
Pilot testing: SP experiments testing (all cases studies)	IST-ID	40	2															█																											
Revisions of the survey and time use diary in MOTUS	ZEW	42	3																						█																				
Launch of the employee survey	UNIZA	45	10																						█																				
Launch of the time use diary (Spring 2025)																																													

3.7. Expected outcomes

The expected outputs of this study are:

- Cleaned and anonymised datasets (for all case studies combined) compiled from employee surveys (published at later stages of the WW4WL),
- Cleaned and anonymised datasets (for all case studies combined) compiled from time diaries (published at later stages of the WW4WL),
- Cleaned and anonymised datasets (for all case studies combined) compiled from the in-depth interviews (published at later stages of the WW4WL),
- A dataset to complement data sources used to forecast RWA trends in T6.1 and inform modelling of travel behaviour patterns in T6.2,
- New knowledge and a better understanding of the socio-economic effects of RWA from an employee's perspective (see Section 3.1.1),
- A series of articles in scientific journals presenting the findings and conclusions derived from analysis of collected data (T8.2).

3.8. Expected scientific and social benefits

The scientific benefits of collected data are given by new knowledge and understanding regarding RWA socio-economic impacts from the employee's perspective (Table 22). This concerns the impacts of RWA on the work-life balance, quality of life, and quality of time. Attention will be paid to individual-company interactions and how RWA impacts mental health. Further, a new light will be shed on the effectiveness of different tools in reducing the digital divide. Decisions regarding residential and job locations will be studied based on the SP experiment. Knowledge derived from this analysis will be used in WP6 to inform models and in the final effect better understand the potential impacts of RWA on the environment and land use. It can be used to navigate employers and employees regarding location decisions. To close the loop, the legal and security rules will be mapped for a selected cross-border area (Luxembourg-centred cross-border region) and studied to understand the consequences of taxation mechanisms for RWA scenarios. The gained knowledge will be published and fed into policy recommendations and this way WW4WL will inform policy makers, but also employers and employees on how to set and implement strategies that can maximise the social and economic benefits of RWA.

4. Protocol for the digital nomad survey

4.1. Aim

The digital nomad survey is a standalone survey run in Portugal only. The aim of the digital nomad survey is to explore in more detail the impact of digital nomads on the urban structure, for example, how digital nomads move around in the city to understand its gentrification impacts (the survey will be complemented by secondary data – collected from public statistics, which includes contextual variables like housing prices and retail establishments), and economic impacts in terms of changing service provision (e.g., restaurants, cafés, etc).

4.2. Study design

In general, little is known about digital nomads and their actual number in Portugal and in particular in Lisbon Metropolitan Area. Because of the exploratory nature of this target group, it is not possible to predefine a sampling frame. Only the following general guidelines can be specified:

- Focus on Lisbon Metropolitan Area,
- Cover both official (paying taxes and having working permits) and ‘under-the-radar’ digital nomads.

To streamline the process at project level and similar to the employee study, the digital nomad survey will be, if possible, designed in MOTUS, which gives the opportunity to also invite digital nomads for time diaries and in-depth interviews. Consent will be obtained accordingly.

4.3. Survey content and structure

Besides socioeconomic data, the survey will focus on several topics related with the decision location processes, ranging from the choice of city to live to the characteristics of the chosen neighbourhood and house. It will include also questions about their satisfaction with their current location and their perception about their impacts on the neighbourhoods where they live. The survey will also include questions about their working habits and general travel behaviour (including leisure trips), to be complemented by a multiple day travel diary.

4.4. Expected outcomes

The expected outputs of this study are:

- Cleaned and anonymised datasets compiled from the digital nomad survey and complemented with the secondary data about housing prices and retail establishments (published at later stages of the WW4WL),
- New knowledge and a better understanding of the impacts of digital nomads, with a particular emphasis on gentrification processes,
- A series of articles in scientific journals presenting the findings and conclusions derived from analysis of the collected data (T8.2).

4.5. Expected scientific and social benefits

The scientific benefits of the collected data about digital nomads are given by new knowledge and understanding regarding their impacts on the cities where they chose to locate. This concerns the impacts on gentrification and economic impacts in terms of changing service provision and the spatial distribution of retail establishments (which could also contribute to gentrification). The data collected in the surveys will be used to estimate models aimed at disentangling the role of digital nomads in the gentrification processes experienced in the case study of Lisbon. Knowledge derived from the analysis will be used in WP6 to inform policymaking regarding the potential impacts of digital nomadism. The gained knowledge will be published and fed into policy recommendations and this way WW4WL will inform policy makers, on how to set and implement strategies that can maximise the potential benefits of digital nomadism while at the same time be effective in reducing their negative effects.

5. Ethical considerations

WW4WL is a data rich project. At each step of the data collection, we will carefully evaluate what data is really needed in order to avoid the collection of data that are not strictly speaking necessary. In general, we will not collect information considered sensitive personal data, such as sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction. However, we will collect information on home and workplace location (via questions in the online employee survey). We do this not because we are interested in those locations per se, but to be able to geocode these locations and thus add spatial information about these locations (e.g., density, distance to public transport) needed for the statistical analyses in WP5. Moreover, GPS tracks will be collected from employees who will complete the time diaries via the mobile MOTUS app. The app automatically tracks geolocation needed to automatically derive information regarding activity and travel behaviour characteristics (e.g., duration of out-of-home activities, trip distance, trip chaining, transport mode) during a post-processing phase in WP6. No analysis on the location data per se will thus be performed. Addresses (name of the street, building number, postcode) and GPS tracks will not appear in the final open database. We will be extra careful that aggregation of different data collections does not lead to re-identification and de-anonymization of participants. At no time will any participant's identity or location data appear in documents intended for the public or other institutions. In case of publication or presentation needs, we will exclusively rely on theoretical examples.

The data collection does not target vulnerable groups in particular. However, understanding equity and especially gender equity in the RWA impacts on living and working conditions is an important objective of the project. Therefore, data analyses will pay attention to the heterogeneity of the effects across population groups, in particular gender and its intersectionalities with age, sector of employment, company size, and location (urban, rural, cross-border).

Research participants will maintain research anonymity unless declaring otherwise, and will receive the assurance that all discussions are confidential. The project will survey a group of adults aged above 20 years old. They can only participate with written consent and on a voluntary basis. In each step of the data collection, participants will be clearly explained what data is gathered, who has access to it (i.e., consortium members) and how it will be processed (i.e., for research purposes only). The collected data will be firstly analysed within the scope of the project. Towards the end of the project, an anonymised dataset will be openly released to the public to stimulate further research on this topic. More information about how data will be managed, processed, exploited, curated, and preserved can be found in D1.2 *Data management plan*.

Moreover, an appropriate Consent Form and Information Sheet will be prepared for each phase in the data collection (i.e., employer survey, employee survey, time diaries, in-depth interviews, digital nomad survey). It is currently assumed that countries'

informed Consent Forms and Information Sheet are prepared within the employee survey and can be reused for the time diary study, given that participants will flow from the employee survey to the time diary study. This is not necessarily the case for the in-depth interviews as only a specific selection of participants to the time diary study will flow to the in-depth interviews and this will probably require a separate Consent Form and Information Sheet, these documents will be translated in the official languages of the countries where the data are collected. Approvals of these Consent Forms and Information Sheets from the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) of each country in which data collection takes place will be obtained before the beginning of the data collection.

Local data collection teams will also seek ethical approval with their institutional research ethics committee before data collection starts.

6. Conclusion

This report provides a harmonised plan for data collections to be conducted in five WW4WL geographic areas. The report documents the outcome of the effort to achieve an agreement among WW4WL partners on general principles to be followed, while many low-level decisions (e.g., exact formulation of invitation emails and letters, concrete workflow of communication steps with respondents, or steps to be taken as a part of the data collection monitoring ensuring data quality, etc.) will be taken as a part of the implementation process and in the continuing biweekly WP3 progress meetings. The data collection processes involve many dependencies that need to be tested as part of the survey designs, particularly in terms of 1) ensuring all research questions are appropriately covered, 2) ensuring the various data collection instruments make sense as a whole (e.g., questions are not asked twice), and 3) the technical implementations in MOTUS are fully functional. A key moment to this process will be the pilot testing of the studies.

During the data collection phases, there are some potential risks. Some of these risks are a) obtaining an unbalanced and non-representative sample in the employer survey, employee survey and time diary, b) difficulty in finding and contacting digital nomads, and c) low response rates with insufficient participant engagement (few observations) leading to inadequate sample sizes. Once the data collection is running, there will be a need for close monitoring of the campaigns to ensure sample targets are met and potential risks are mitigated. The progress of all data collection steps will be reported in D3.1 in relation to the Implementation plan for data collection.

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